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Developing a Cost Efficient RADAR System

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Abstract: RADAR is an electromagnetic coordination for the detection and location of targeted objects. A radar transmits pulses of radio waves or microwaves which bounce off any object in its trail. Radars have been used for military application, highway patrol, ballistic missile guidance, airport traffic flow control, navigation, positioning, mapping, spying or tracking and many other solicitations. In this paper we've shown how we developed a resourceful cost efficient tech using basic components that reflects all the possible techniques a radar consists of. It uses ultrasonic sensors to identify objects in range and passes the data to Arduino microcontroller. Arduino UNO board is sufficed to control ultrasonic sensor, the movement of it and also to interface the sensor with digital display. The prototype of the system is implemented and coding for Arduino control is developed. Experimental results show that the system can detect objects within the range with high accuracy and perfect for indoor applications.

Keywords : Microwave, Ultrasonic Sensor, Arduino, RADAR

Introduction:

RADAR is an exemplary artifact of an electronic engineering structure that develops under many of the specialized fundamentals of technology practiced by electrical engineers including signal processing, data processing, waveform design, electromagnetic scattering, detection, parameter estimation, information extraction, antennas, propagation transmitters, and receivers. RADAR was developed by various nations before and during Second World War. The term RADAR itself, not the actual development, was coined in 1940 by the United States Navy as an acronym for Radio Detection and Ranging. Radar framework arrives in an assortment distinctive performance particulars. Some radars are applied as aviation authority at air terminals and others are utilized

for long range observation and early-cautioning frameworks. Recently it has been seen in the self-parking car systems advertised by Audi, Ford and even the upcoming driverless cars by Google, Tesla, Volvo and BMW. The development projected by us can be installed in any systems the handler may want to use like in a car, a bicycle or anything else. The use of Arduino in the project provides even more flexibility of usage of the aforementioned module according to the requirements.

Related Work:

It was found that the idea of radar tech is searched a lot and is a mainstream idea which is still in advance. The advanced system how effective and solid they are were not financially achievable.

The indication of constructing an Ultrasonic RADAR came as a part of a study carried out on the working and mechanism of “Automobiles of Future”. Intelligent driver monitoring and vehicle control system is introduced to avoid accidents by monitoring the driver’s activities. The key reasons of accidents nowadays are alcohol consumption by the driver, carelessness, drowsiness or medical illness. The various units in the framework, including motors, relays, power unit and ESP8299 module are tried and are observed to be in working condition. Ultrasonic sensor is utilized to alarm the driver if any vehicle draws close to his vehicle. ^[1]

There is a paper represents a system for obstacle detection in a known environment for visually impaired people. This research is about a blind walking stick made for blind people through which they can avoid obstacles while they walk and avoid collision. The author proposed a mapping algorithm using SONAR and laser cameras which he claimed derived an output of 96% accuracy. In this paper presented an intention for identifying interference in known situation with an android based adaptable camera which scans selected territory before the camera for impediment location. ^[2]

Components Required:

a. Hardware Specification

Arduino UNO - The Arduino Uno is a microcontroller board based on the ATmega328. It has 14 digital Input /Output pins (of which 6 can be used as PWM outputs), 6 analog inputs, a 16MHz ceramic resonator, USB connection, a power jack, an ICSP header and a reset button. It contains

everything needed to support the microcontroller; simply connect it to computer with a USB cable or power it with a AC-to-DC adapter or battery to get started. [3]

Ultrasonic Sensor - Ultrasonic sensors (similarly recognized as transceivers when they both send and receive, but more generally called transducers) work on a principle alike radar or sonar which evaluate qualities of a target by interpreting the echoes from radio or sound waves respectively. Ultrasonic sensors generate high frequency sound waves and evaluate the echo which is received back by the sensor. Sensors calculate the time interval between sending the signal and receiving the echo to determine the distance to an object. The model of ultrasonic sensor we are using for this is HC 120. [4]

Servo Motor - A servomotor is a rotary actuator that permits for defined control of angular position, velocity and acceleration. It comprises a suitable motor coupled to a sensor for position feedback. It also requires a relatively sophisticated controller, often a dedicated module designed specifically for use with servomotors. Servomotors are not a different class of motor, on the basis of fundamental operating principle, but uses servomechanism to achieve closed loop control with a generic open loop motor. Servomotors are used in applications such as robotics, CNC machinery or automated manufacturing. [5]

Jumper wires and breadboard is also needed for connection purpose

b. Software Specification

Arduino IDE – The Arduino Integrated Development Environment (IDE) is a cross-platform application that is written in functions from C and C++. It is used to write and upload programs to Arduino compatible boards, but also, with the help of 3rd party cores, other vendor development boards. It is designed to introduce programming to artists and other newcomers unfamiliar with software development. It includes a code editor with features such as syntax highlighting, brace matching, and automatic indentation, and is also capable of compiling and uploading programs to the board with a single click. [6]

Processing – integrated development environment (IDE) built for the electronic arts, new media art, and visual design communities with the purpose of teaching the fundamentals of computer

programming in a visual context, and to serve as the foundation for electronic sketchbooks. The project was initiated in 2001 by Casey Reas and Benjamin Fry, both formerly of the Aesthetics and Computation Group at the MIT Media Lab. One of the stated aims of Processing is to act as a tool to get non-programmers started with programming, through the instant gratification of visual feedback. The language builds on the Java language, but uses a simplified syntax and graphics programming models.

Design and Implementation:

Arduino program uploaded by IDE is responsible to control all interfaced devices. For moving the radar we arranged automotive robotics structure. Arduino commands the motor driver IC (L293D IC) to turn clockwise and anti-clockwise when required. A user defined command program can be set via Arduino IDE according to user’s requirement. Arduino program compare this code with the predefined code. If it is match then program gives digital signal to motor driver IC and perform the required operation like left, right, forward and backward.

Theoretically Arduino can control the servo motor in angle of 0 to 180 degree. On this servo motor we are putting ultrasonic sensor which is connected to the Arduino board. Ultrasonic sensor works on the trigger and echo pulse. As per object distance it will generate echo pulse. If object is having less distance than threshold distance saved in program then program will find out the angle of servo motor and show existence of object in processing display.

Working:

After its designing, construction and programming we begin to test our prototype. We placed few objects in front of the ultrasonic sensor. As the motor rotates, our monitor starts to display the output through processing IDE. Hence, when the sensor crossed over the object it showed a red segment with the distance and angle where the object is placed.

The block diagram explains how this radar system works. The sensor is going to sense the obstacle and determine the angle of incident and its distance from the radar. The servo motor is constantly rotating to and fro, hence making the sensor move. The data obtained is encoded and fed to the processing IDE which represents it on the screen. The results are displayed further in this paper. All these operation are done by Arduino microcontroller from the rotation of the servo, data collection from the sensor, feeding the data to encoder to transferring it to the display.

The goal of our design is to ascertain the distance position and speed of the obstacle set at some distance from the sensor. Ultrasonic sensor sends electromagnetic wave in various ways by rotating via servo motors. This wave goes in air reflected back subsequent while striking some object. This wave is detected back by the same sensor and its qualities is analyzed and output is shown in screen indicating parameters, for example, distance and position of object. Arduino IDE is utilized to compose code and transfer coding in Arduino and causes us to detect position or angle of servo motor and it is communicated through the serial port alongside the covered distance of the nearest object in its way. Output of all of this working is shown in the software called processing, it will display the input/output and the range of the object. ^[7]

Discussion and Result:

The prototype we designed signify its received information graphically, hence its output will be represented through processing software. We can have an idea of efficiency of this radar by testing objects at different levels and witness how quicker or effortlessly it detects an object.

Following figures express the results of the monitor screen of our design when the sensor rotates through the area and detects an obstacle in the way. The red area indicates the presence of an obstacle and below the angle of incidence and distance is being displayed.

Testing of the system:

- a) Object 1 is placed 30.5 far from the radar, radar gives the distance 32 cm, so:
- o $\text{error} = (32 - 30.5) / 30.5 * 100 = 4.918\%$
 - o $\text{efficiency 1} = 100 - \text{error} = 95.08\%$

- b) Object 2 placed at a distance of 20.3 cm, radar gives the distance 21 cm so:
- o $\text{error} = ((21 - 20.3) / 20.3) * 100 = 3.44\%$
 - o $\text{efficiency 2} = 100 - \text{error} = 96.55\%$

Future Work:

This prototype reflects the basic working principle of mainstream radar technology. This prototype is limited by its hardware specification because we tried to make a low-cost device. The information flow is wired right now, but in the future we plan to make it over a secure encrypted WIFI channel that has camera-enabled features. This system can only detect objects from 0 to 180 degrees only because the servo motor that we have used can rotate only to this range. So, due to this limitation, our design cannot be applied to places or areas for obstacle detection on a larger scale. Usage of a 360-degree rotating servo motor can make the system more efficient. We look forward to modify

this system and enhance our research work by using a fully 360 degrees rotating servo and a higher ranged ultrasonic sensor.

Conclusion:

Several cutting-edge mechanism gave designers to have more command over different advanced applications. In our paper, the recommended Arduino based radar system mapping method of whole system is assessed on small principles or scale. ^[8] As we have designed a short range radar therefore our research was specified and limited. The field that we have chosen for our design “Radar System” is a very vast field and future scope of this technology is very high. We have tremendous applications in which radar system have been implemented or used. ^[9] There is a lot of future scope of this design because of its security capacity. It can be used in many applications. This framework can also be developed or modified according to the rising needs and demand

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